

Effect of Benzoyl Chloride and Fiber Loading on Mechanical Properties and Biodegradation of Poly Lactic Acid/Sugarcane Bagasse Fibre Composites

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ABSTRACT:

This study aimed to investigate the properties of benzoyl chloride modified and unmodified poly lactic acid and sugarcane bagasse fibre composites (PLA/SCBF), as well as the impact of chemical treatment on the mechanical and biodegradation properties of these composites. In this study, Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy was employed to examine the benzoyl chloride modified and unmodified fibre samples. Additionally, Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and Thermal Gravimetric Analysis (TGA) techniques were utilised to investigate the morphology and thermal behaviour of the Poly lactic/SCBF composites. The results indicate that the use of benzoyl chloride treatment resulted in an increase in the tensile, flexural characteristics, impact strength, and hardness strength. The treatment with benzoyl chloride resulted in a reduction in both water absorption and biodegradability. The research also elucidated the impact of increasing the quantity of sugar cane bagasse on the aforementioned qualities. The addition of SCBF at higher loading resulted in a decrease in the tensile strength, biodegradability, flexural strength, and impact strength. The water absorption and hardness exhibited a positive correlation with the increase in fibre loading. The observed improvement in mechanical characteristics indicates that the treatment effectively enhanced the interfacial adhesion between SCBF and the PLA matrix. The enhancement of the interfacial adhesive forces was observed by the examination of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs. The Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrum of the treated solvent-cast bamboo fibre (SCBF) exhibited the presence of a benzoyl group attached to the fibre, indicating successful benzoyl chloride treatment. Additionally, a modest reduction in hemicellulose content was seen following the treatment. The thermal characteristics of the modified PLA/SCBF composites were found to be enhanced based on the results obtained from the TGA-DTA analysis.

Keywords: Absorption, treatment, biopolymers, thermal properties, composites.

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, research has been targeted towards solving the environmental concerns associated with the increasingly high level of carbon (IV) oxide emission as a result of increasing industrial activities which is also associated with global warming [1]. Environmental pollution has also been a great issue due to the increasing use of plastics and plastic products. Biopolymers such as, polyhydroxylalkanote, polylactic acid, poly (butyleneadipate-co-terephthalete) can be used as a substitute for these plastic materials and hence solve the environmental challenges they impose [2]

The shift from the utilisation of environmentally detrimental plastics to a more sustainable alternative is contingent upon the adoption of bio-based composite materials. As a result, the utilisation of natural fibres as reinforcement in bio-based composite materials has been observed [3].

The engineering of composite materials involves the integration of many materials, each with distinct physical or chemical properties. Through its combination, a composite material is created, exhibiting unique features that differ from those of its constituent materials. The characteristics commonly shown by composites encompass enhanced strength and stiffness due to the presence of fibres inside a matrix that possesses comparatively lower strength and stiffness. The objective is to produce a component that possesses enhanced strength and stiffness while maintaining a low density [4].

However, the utilisation of natural fibres in composite materials is frequently associated with several drawbacks, primarily stemming from the inherent disparities in size and mechanical properties among these fibres, even when they are derived from comparable sources. According to Lee et al. [5], if there is a shortage in the fibre used for reinforcements, it can result in stress concentration inside the composites. According to Hughes [6], it is hypothesised that these imperfections serve as a catalyst for the initiation of cracks and subsequent separation between the fibre and matrix. Additionally, a significant limitation that restricts the use of natural fibres in composite manufacturing is their inadequate thermal stability. This deficiency leads to the degradation of the final composite as a consequence of fibre disintegration when exposed to elevated temperatures. Natural fibres possess inherent hydrophilic properties due to the abundance of hydroxyl groups and other polar groups present within their structure. This phenomenon gives rise to their limited capacity to establish contact with the surface, leading to incompatibility within the hydrophobic polymer matrix and feeble adhesion at the fiber-matrix interface [7]. There exist numerous challenges pertaining to the interface between natural fibres and biodegradable polymers.

Numerous methodologies have been investigated to enhance the mechanical characteristics of these biocomposites. One of the strategies employed is the surface modification of cellulose, which can be accomplished through chemical treatment utilising certain chemical agents referred to as coupling agents. Another approach involves the application of heat as a means of treatment. According to the study conducted by Kaewskuk *et al.* [8], Chemical coupling agents are regarded as chemical substrates that undergo reactions with the hydroxyl group of cellulose and the functional group of the polymer.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Preparation of the Stock Solution

The 10% NaOH preparation was done by dissolving 10g of sodium hydroxide pallets in 100ml of distilled water and stirred until the NaOH was dissolved completely. The 6 % NaOH was prepared by dissolving 6g.

Sample Collection and Preparation

Analytical grade poly lactic acid was obtained from HAFASON Chemicals Ltd., sugarcane Bagasse was collected from Rigasa Local Market, in Kaduna State Nigeria. The collected Bagasse was sorted to remove foreign matters. 1000 g of the sorted the weight of the bagasse was noted before drying under the sun and to a constant weight of 650 g for elimination of moisture from the Bagasse. The

Bagasse fiber was reduced to 1 mm using a laboratory milling machine and divided into two portions. A portion of the 1 mm milled Bagasse was modified using NaOH and Benzoyl Chloride solution.

Benzoyl chloride treatment of the Bagasse

Approximately 300 grammes of milled Bagasse fibre was immersed in a solution of 6% NaOH for a duration of 30 minutes at ambient temperature. Subsequently, the fibre was filtered and washed with distilled water until the water reached a neutral pH as indicated by litmus paper. The Bagasse that had undergone treatment was thereafter immersed in a separate solution of NaOH at a concentration of 10% w/v. The mixture was then rapidly mixed together with 500 ml of benzoyl chloride. The mixture was permitted to remain undisturbed for a duration of 15 minutes. Subsequently, it was subjected to filtration, followed by rinsing with distilled water and subsequent drying until a consistent weight of 274 g was achieved at ambient temperature. Following the treatment, the bagasse was subsequently submerged in a flask containing a solution consisting of 90% ethanol. The mixture was then allowed to remain undisturbed for approximately one hour. This was done so as to eliminate unreacted benzoyl chloride then was finally rinsed using distilled water. Followed by drying to a weight of 250g.

Composites Fabrication

Table 1. Formation of the composites at different loading of SCBF by weight

Sample	Treated Bagasse (g)	PLA (g)
Control	0	100
A _T	5	95
B _T	10	90
C _T	15	85
D _T	20	80
E _T	25	75

Composites consisting of poly lactic acid as matrix and sugarcane Bagasse as reinforcement (PLA/SCB) were compounded using a two-roll milling machine as described by Wan Azani *et al.* [9]. In this process, the biopolymer (PLA) was introduced into the rotating rolls of the two roll milling machine, the rolls was set at counter clockwise rotation. The mixing was done for About 3 minutes at 160°C. When there was a band formation of PLA, the Fiber (bagasse) was added at the rotation of the roles was set to 50 revolutions per minutes which b was allowed to mix thoroughly for even distribution of fiber and polymer. This process was done for aboiut 5 minutes. Then the composites were sheeted out and letter labelled as in table 1 above [9]. The same procedure was followed for the other treated samples and the designated control (Neat sample), A_T, B_T, C_T, D_T and E_T.

Compression Molding of the Composites

The composite material resulting from the mixing process was poured into a metal mould with dimensions of 150 mm x 100 mm x 3 mm. Additionally, specific metal moulds were designed for the purpose of conducting tensile, impact strength, hardness, and flexural strength tests, following the guidelines outlined in ASTM D-638(2010), ASTM D 156, ASTM D 2240, and ASTM D-790. After which the filled moulds were placed on the hydraulic hot press machine for shaping at 150°C and 2.5 MPa for 5minutes. It was transferred to a cool platen for cooling under pressure of 2.5 MPa for 3 minutes.

Water Uptake Test

The designated sample size for the water absorption experiment was 50 millimetres by 50 millimetres by 3 millimetres.

The experiment involved immersing the sample completely in distilled water at room temperature for a duration of four weeks. At weekly intervals, the samples were taken out and any water present on the surface of the specimens was meticulously removed. The increase in weight was duly seen using a digital weighing scale. The measurement of water absorption by the composite material was conducted using the weight gain method. The standard reference for measuring the water absorption of plastics is ASTM D570.

The calculation of water uptake was performed using the subsequent equation:

$$\% \text{Water Absorbed} = \frac{W_t - W_i}{W_i} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

W_i = initial Weight (g)

W_t = Final Weight (g)

Characterization of prepared composites

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FT-IR studies of both treated and untreated SCB fibre were conducted using the FTIR thermal Nicolet with Model no: Nexus 870, operating within the wave number range of 4000 - 650 cm^{-1} (Salisu *et al.*, 2015).

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Analysis

In order to examine the morphology of the broken composite sample, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was conducted on the selected AT, CT, AU, and CU specimens, following the guidelines outlined in the ASTM D E986 standard, as documented by Salisu *et al.* [10].

Thermo-gravimetric analysis

The evaluation of the thermal stability of benzoyl chloride modified and unmodified samples at 5% SCBF loading was carried out on the sample by heating from 30 to 950°C at a heating rate 10°C/min.

Biodegradation

The test to examine the biodegradability of the composites was carried out by burying method as described by Harmaen *et al.* [11]. In this experimental procedure, samples of natural soil were obtained and measures were taken to ensure the absence of any composting material or enzymatic activity inside the soil. The specimens subjected to treatment were interred within the soil substrate for a duration of 80 days. The samples were retrieved at regular intervals of 20 days. The retrieved samples were subjected to a rinsing process using running water in order to remove any residual soil. Subsequently, the samples were subjected to oven drying at a temperature of 800°C to eradicate any remaining moisture. The quantification of weight loss subsequent to soil burial serves as an indicator of the biodegradability of the samples. This measurement was determined by employing the following methodology:

$$\text{Weight loss (\%)} = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where W_0 stands for the weight of samples prior to testing and W_t stands for weight of samples after completion of test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Analysis of Mechanical Properties

Tensile Test

The tensile strengths, modulus at break and elongation curve for modified and unmodified bio composites at varying SCB filler loadings are shown below in Fig 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 2. Tensile Strength Test Result

Sample	Load (N)	Extension (mm)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Strain	Modulus at Break (MPa)
Control	1087.50	6.00	28.32	0.120	236.000
A _T	1208.33	6.84	31.41	0.137	229.708
B _T	1000.00	5.78	26.04	0.116	224.488
C _T	733.33	3.64	19.10	0.073	261.644
D _T	712.50	3.36	18.55	0.067	276.866
E _T	575.00	2.76	14.97	0.055	272.182
A _U	958.33	5.00	24.96	0.100	249.600
B _U	725.00	3.00	18.88	0.060	314.667
C _U	600.00	2.92	15.63	0.058	269.488
D _U	550.00	3.48	14.32	0.070	204.571
E _U	508.33	2.48	13.24	0.050	264.800

Figure 1. Illustrates the Impact of Benzoyl Chloride Treatment and the Addition of Sugarcane Bagasse Filler on the Tensile Strength of PLA/SCBF Composites

Figure 2. Illustrates the Impact of Benzoyl Chloride Treatment and the Addition of Sugarcane Bagasse Filler on the Tensile Strength of PLA/SCBF Composites

Figure 3. Illustrates the Impact of Benzoyl Chloride Treatment and the Specific Heat Build-up Factor (SCBF) on the Elongation of the Poly(lactic Acid) (PLA)/SCBF Composite

It was observed that there was a decline in elongation, increase in break modulus, also, decreases of the tensile strength especially for the untreated composites upon addition of SCBF (figure 1). The hydrophilic nature of untreated SCBF is primarily attributed to the presence of hemicellulose, lignin, and cellulose in the natural fibre. These components have the ability to absorb water, thereby hindering the strong adhesion between SCBF and the PLA matrix. Consequently, the inadequate

interfacial force leads to the formation of numerous voids at the bonding junction of SCBF and PLA. These voids can serve as potential sites for cracks and fiber-polymer de-bonding. As a result, an increase in the SCBF content in the fabricated biocomposites leads to a decrease in their tensile properties. These findings align with the research conducted by Chatrapati *et al.* in 2015 [12].

Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that the PLA/SCBF composites modified with benzoyl chloride exhibited a notable enhancement in tensile strength, even when the SCBF content remained constant. This improvement can be attributed to the replacement of a significant portion of the hydroxyl groups, which are responsible for the hydrophilic characteristics of the SCBF, with benzoyl groups that possess lower hydrophilicity. Consequently, the modification of the fibre resulted in an increased interfacial force of attraction between the fibre and polymer matrix, thereby contributing to the observed increase in tensile strength. This observation is consistent with the research by Li *et al.* [7].

In figure 2, 236MPa is the value of modulus for unreinforced PLA matrix MPa, the tensile modulus enhanced upon with addition of more SCBF and the enhancement was seen in both composites, however it was observed that at 15% loading of the SCBF, the benzoyl chloride treated composites began to show better modulus at break than the untreated composite.

Figure 3 shows that the elongation of PLA/SCBF composites reduced drastically with increase in fiber loading, which is as a result of the enhancement in stiffness upon increasing SCB fillers. However, there is an increase in elongation of break at 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20% fiber loading of the composites treated with benzoyl chloride, The observed improvement can be due to the effective dispersion and strong interfacial bonding between the SCBF and PLA matrix, resulting in enhanced stress transmission from the matrix to the SCB fibre phase. Nevertheless, as the SCB loading reached 25%, a significant reduction in elongation of the treated composites was observed. The observed phenomenon can be attributed to the heightened discontinuity of the PLA matrix resulting from the substantial loading of SCBF. Additionally, when fillers were loaded at high levels, the transmission of stress from the matrix to the fillers was impeded as a result of agglomeration and the contact between fibres. This finding conformed to findings that was reported by Abdul Majid *et al.*, [13]. Since the rigidity of SCBF is more than that of pure PLA matrix, this leads to increase in modulus when incorporated with SCBF.

Hardness Test

The data and numerical results of hardness test for both treated and untreated bio composites are presented.

Table 3. Hardness Test Result

Sample	Hardness Strength			Average Hardness Strength (Hv)
	1 st (Hv)	2 nd (Hv)	3 rd (Hv)	
Control	72.7	72.6	72.0	72.43
A _T	77.1	76.9	77.2	77.07
B _T	80.0	80.2	80.0	80.07
C _T	80.9	80.8	81.2	80.97
D _T	82.4	82.3	82.3	82.33
E _T	81.9	81.7	81.6	81.73
A _U	76.5	76.4	77.1	76.67
B _U	77.2	77.0	77.9	77.37
C _U	78.3	78.1	78.5	78.30
D _U	68.2	68.7	68.0	68.30
E _U	62.8	61.5	62.6	62.30

Figure 4. Illustrates the Impact of Benzoyl Chloride Treatment and SCBF Loading on the Hardness Strength of Both Modified and Untreated PLA/SCBF Composites

The hardness results of pure poly lactic acid matrix and also for treated and untreated composites at 5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25% loading of SCBF filler are showed in figure 4. There is a relationship between hardness and topology of the SCBF surface, this is because each of the SCBF fiber forms an interface individually with the matrix. The results depicted in Figure 4 indicate that the hardness strength of the untreated PLA/SCBF composites exhibits a minor rise with increasing SCBF fillers, up to a loading of 15%. However, a subsequent fall in hardness strength is observed as the loading is further raised to 20% and 25%. The benzoyl chloride treated composites as expected showed increased hardness at 10%, 15%, and 20% SCBF loading but decreases slightly at 25% SCBF loading. The enhancement in hardness is due to the higher fiber- matrix interaction and enhanced compatibility and wetting. Results of similar findings as reported by Ventatesha and Venkata [14] suggest that chemical modification of natural fiber yields composites of greater hardness strength as distinguished to the untreated bio composites.

Flexural test

The flexural strength, also known as the modulus of rupture, is a mechanical property that measures the ability of a material to resist bending or breaking under an applied load. Table 4 presents the flexural parameters of the pure PLA matrix and PLA/SCB composites, both treated with benzoyl chloride and untreated. The composites were loaded with SCBF at varying concentrations of 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25%.

Table 4. Flexural Strength Test Result

Sample	Breaking Load (N)	Deflection			Modulus of Rupture (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (MPa)
		Initial (mm)	Final (mm)	Deflection "D" (mm)		
Control	1942.000	25.21	28.61	3.40	93.216	109.660
A _T	2214.580	25.15	28.36	3.21	106.300	132.460
B _T	2327.600	25.24	28.21	2.97	111.725	153.380
C _T	1932.292	25.22	27.62	2.40	92.750	154.583
D _T	1716.927	25.40	27.45	2.05	82.412	160.804
E _T	1550.320	25.42	27.38	1.96	74.415	151.868
A _u	2102.871	25.31	28.23	2.92	100.938	138.270
B _u	1998.542	25.40	28.04	2.64	95.930	145.348
C _u	1826.650	25.22	27.49	2.27	87.679	154.500
D _u	1664.780	25.32	27.28	1.82	79.909	175.625
E _u	2102.871	25.31	28.23	2.92	100.938	138.270

Figure 5. Illustrates the Impact of Benzoyl Chloride Treatment and SCBF Loading on the Modulus of Rupture of Both Benzoyl Chloride Modified and Untreated PLA/SCBF Composites

Figure 6. Illustrates the Impact of Benzoyl Chloride Treatment and SCBF Loading on the Modulus of Elasticity of Both Modified and Untreated SCBF/PLA Composites

Based on the findings depicted in Figure 5, the incorporation of SCBF into the material leads to a decrease in flexural strength and an increase in modulus of elasticity when compared to the pure PLA. Table 4 illustrates that the greatest flexibility strength is observed for the treated PLA/SCBF at 10% fiber loading while the lowest flexural strength was recorded for PLA incorporated with 25% by weight of SCBF. The potential cause for the decrease in flexural strength observed in fibre reinforced bio composites may be attributed to inadequate fiber-matrix bonding, insufficient wetting of the fibre inside the matrix, and the use of aged and dry fibres [15]. At higher fiber loading a weak interface is created as a result of raising numbers of fiber-fiber interaction. This cause lower flexural strength at greater content of SCBF, also SCBF were not perfectly distributed with the continuous matrix phase, this leads to the creation of void and dispersion problem [15].

However, figure 5 shows that, when the fiber was treated with benzoyl chloride there as increasing the flexural strength of PLA/SCB composites at all fiber loading. The benzoyl chloride treated composites shows increase in flexural strength even at high fiber loadings which conforms to the results of Abdul Majid *et al.* [13]. Furthermore, it was noted that the flexural modulus of benzoyl chloride modified and unmodified bio composite increase with addition of more SCBF, contrary to trend observed in the flexural strength. As observed from figure 6, the benzoyl treatment does not necessary improve the flexural modulus.

Impact Test

From both Table 5 and Figure 7, it can be noticed that as increasing of SCBF lead to a decline in the impact strength of all the biocomposites. As stiffness of natural fiber leads to reduction in chain movement of polymer; as a result there is reduced tendency of PLA matrix to withstand impact energy during failure.

Table 5. Impact Strength Test Results

Sample	Impact Energy				Impact Strength (J/mm)
	1 st (J)	2 nd (J)	3 rd (J)	Average (J)	
Control	0.820	0.798	0.825	0.814	0.163
A _T	0.896	0.891	0.899	0.895	0.179
B _T	0.952	0.961	0.946	0.953	0.191
C _T	0.763	0.749	0.757	0.756	0.151
D _T	0.584	0.587	0.569	0.580	0.116
E _T	0.517	0.519	0.499	0.512	0.102
A _U	0.762	0.790	0.786	0.779	0.156
B _U	0.798	0.791	0.796	0.795	0.159
C _U	0.683	0.645	0.672	0.667	0.133

D _U	0.487	0.493	0.458	0.479	0.096
E _U	0.429	0.398	0.390	0.406	0.081

Figure 7. Illustrates the Impact of Benzoyl Chloride Modification and the Loading of Short Carbon Fibre Bundles (SCBF) on the Impact Strength of the Composite Material Composed of Polylactic Acid (PLA) and SCBF

According to the data presented in Figure 7, the incorporation of benzoyl chloride in the modification of SCBF resulted in an increase in the impact strength of the PLA/SCBF composite. The largest enhancement in impact strength was seen when the SCBF loading was at 10%, as shown in Figure 8. The increased impact strength observed in composites treated with benzoyl chloride can be attributed to the surface modification achieved through the application of a coupling agent. This modification enhances the force of attraction between the SCBF and PLA interfaces, leading to a fracture of the reinforced fibre rather than fibre pull-out. The impact strength of study by Rajesh and Ratna, (2015) also presented higher impact strength of treated PLA/Sisal fiber.

Water Absorption

Figure 8. Illustrates the Impact of Benzoyl Chloride Treatment and Fibre Loading on the Water Absorption Characteristics of the PLA/SCBF Composite

The purpose of conducting the water uptake test was to investigate the impact of SCBF loading and chemical treatment on the rate of water absorption of the produced biocomposites. The results were presented (figure 8). From the obtained results, it showed neat PLA having the lowest water uptake characteristic. This is because PLA polymer behaves like petroleum based polymers which are hydrophobic in nature. The results also suggest that, introduction of SCB increases the water uptake. After few weeks of the test, the absorption of water causes the natural SCBF to swell and results to fiber expansion. This is as a result of the huge amount of hydrophilic group that are present on the SCBF. Nevertheless, the findings indicate a downward trajectory in water absorption for PLA/SCB composites that have been treated with benzoyl chloride. The observed phenomenon can be attributed to the substitution of a significant number of hydrophilic OH groups with benzoyl groups, as evidenced by the Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrum. Similar findings was reported by Chung *et al.* [2].

Fourier Transformation Infra-Red Spectroscopy

Figure 9. Displays the Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) Spectra of (a) Bagasse Fibre that Has Undergone Treatment and (b) Bagasse Fibre that Has Not Undergone Treatment

The Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra of both the modified and unmodified Short Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composite (SCBF) have been depicted in figures (a) and (b) respectively. The purpose of the experiment was to confirm the occurrence of a reaction between benzoyl chloride and the substance present in the SCBF. The presence of functional groups observed in the spectra of both modified and unmodified SCBF provides insight into the occurrence of a coupling reaction. The unaltered spectral correlation-based filter (SCBF) exhibited prominent peaks at wavenumbers of 1237.5 cm⁻¹, 3324.8 cm⁻¹, 1032.5 cm⁻¹, and 1722.0 cm⁻¹. Additionally, there were peaks seen in the range of 1100-1600 cm⁻¹, with a specific peak at 1377.86 cm⁻¹. The observed peak at 1237.5 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to the presence of a primary alcohol, specifically indicating a C-O stretching vibration. The observed peak at 3324.8 cm⁻¹ and 1032.5 cm⁻¹ corresponds to stretching vibrations associated with the hydroxyl group and C-O bond, respectively.

The peak detected at 1722.0 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the crosslinking of ether and ester bonds, whereas the peaks observed in the range of 1100-1600 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to the hemicellulose content of the unmodified SCBF. Also the observed peak at 1377.86cm⁻¹ correspond to hydroxyl group due to the presence of cellulose in the unmodified SCBF. The peaks seen at 1100-1600cm⁻¹ were also present in the modified SCBF but there was a reduction in intensities of the peak which suggests that there have been some elimination of hemicellulose content in the SCBF.

There was another peak that was noted to be present in the Spectra of the benzoylated SCBF which is the peak at 1400cm⁻¹ to 1600cm⁻¹ this conforms to the C=C stretching vibration usually observed in an aromatic ring compound. Additionally, the spectra of the benzoylated SCBF has a prominent peak at 1736.9 cm⁻¹, which can be attributed to the presence of a carbonyl group. This peak confirms the formation of a benzoylated compound. Salisu *et al*, [10] have published findings that agreed to this result.

Scanning Electron Microscopy

Figure 10. Displays Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) Images of (a) AT, (b) CT, (c) AU, and (d) CU

Figure 10 presents the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs depicting the evaluation of the Au, AT, Cu, and CT samples of the bagasse/PLA composites. The samples exhibit a surface that is distinguished by intermittent white patches, which correspond to the bagasse particles, inside a consistent grey phase that signifies the presence of the PLA matrix. Figure 10(a) and (b) depict samples of gold (Au) and aminothiazole (AT), respectively, exhibiting the presence of white patches that indicate the agglomeration of bagasse within the polylactic acid (PLA) matrix. The observed agglomeration phenomenon may be attributed to a limited amount of filler content present in the samples. Figure 10(b) displays the presence of surface contours that may play a crucial role in establishing mechanical interlocks between the bagasse filler and the PLA material. These interlocks are essential for ensuring adequate stress distribution during mechanical analysis. It is worth noting that this observation pertains specifically to the sample loaded with treated bagasse. Therefore, the observed outcome of the treatment was noted. Figure 10(c) and (d) depict the surface morphology of sample Cu and CT, respectively. These micrographs exhibit a reduced presence of white agglomerates, suggesting a more uniform dispersion of fillers inside the matrix. The potential cause for this phenomenon may be attributed to the presence of a significant amount of filler content in the samples. Additionally, an increased number of surface contours were detected in Figure 10(d). Therefore, a more suitable filler. This aligns with the conclusions provided by Salisu et al. [10].

Thermal Stability

Table 7. Thermo-Gravimetric Analysis (TGA)

Sample	Thermal Degradation Properties			
	T _{onset} (°C)	T _{50%} (°C)	T _{degradation} (°C)	% Residue at 800°C
Au	250	330	410	9.0
A _T	250	470	540	18.0
Cu	312	430	515	5.0
C _T	315	440	518	6.0
Eu	300	410	485	17.0
E _T	310	450	550	5.0

Table 7 Show the various onset temperature of some of the modified and unmodified bio composites to be 250, 250, 312, 315, 300 and 310°C for the tested sample Au, A_T, Cu, C_T, Eu and E_T. Some crucial parameters that were also derived from the TGA thermograph A are T_{50%} which represents the temperature that the composite has lost 50% weight. This is classified as the second region temperature of TGA curve and it describes the decomposition temperature of the tested samples into volatile (gaseous) and residues (solid) components. T_{50%} obtained are 330, 470, 430, 440 410 and 450°C for the sample Au, A_T, Cu, C_T, Eu and E_T respectively. T_{degradation} is the third region of the TGA thermograph. This refers to the temperature of highest degradation rate is obtained, at which no volatile component is left in the sample but the residue. 410, 540, 515, 518, 485 and 550°C were obtained as T_{degradation} for the sample Au, A_T, Cu, C_T, Eu and E_T respectively.

According to a study conducted by Visahk et al. [16], it was observed that when composite materials are subjected to a gradual increase in temperature, the initial effect is the evaporation of moisture and other volatile components. Subsequently, as the material continues to be heated, a portion of it undergoes degradation and is transformed into gaseous products, resulting in a corresponding loss of weight as evidenced by the thermographs obtained from thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Following this, additional heating will eliminate organic substances in the sample, resulting in the retention of solely inorganic stuff as residue. The phenomenon described occurs at the temperature known as the complete degradation temperature, denoted as T₈₀₀. The remaining material from the sample is referred to as the percentage residue at 800 degrees Celsius, with values of 9.0%, 18.0%, 5.0%, 6.0%, 17.0%, and 5.0% for the Au, AT, Cu, CT, Eu, and ET samples, respectively. The results indicate that the onset temperature of the composites exhibits an increasing trend with higher fibre loading. However, it is worth noting that at maximum fibre loading, a slight decrease in the onset temperature was observed in sample Eu. This can be attributed to the accumulation of moisture at higher fibre loading levels, which subsequently leads to a reduction in the onset temperature. An increase in fibre loading was shown to result in an increase in both T_{50%} and T_{degradation}.

Nevertheless, when subjected to benzoyl chloride alteration, there was an apparent elevation in the start temperature, $T_{degradation}$, and T_{50} . The observed phenomenon can be attributed to the enhancement of interfacial adhesion between the fibre and matrix, as well as the elimination of hemicelluloses. These results align with the conclusions reported by Chung et al. [2].

Biodegradability Test

Figure 11. Illustrates the Impact of Benzoyl Chloride Treatment and SCBF Loading on the Biodegradation Process of PLA/SCBF Bio Composites

Figure 11 illustrates the percentage weight loss of the plain PLA matrix, as well as the PLA/SCBF composites treated with benzoyl chloride and those left untreated, at various SCBF loadings ranging from 5% to 25%. The observation was made that an increase in subcutaneous blood flow (SCBF) content has a decelerating effect on the process of weight reduction. The observed outcome can be attributed to the fact that SCBF exhibits a somewhat lower biodegradability compared to the neat PLA matrix. Consequently, the inclusion of SCBF in the matrix leads to an extended duration for biodegradation to occur. A modest decrease in weight loss was seen in the benzoyl chloride treated composites at all levels of fibre loading. The observed phenomenon can be related to the removal of moisture from SCBF, which is essential for biodegradation, as well as an increase in the attractive force at the interphase between SCBF and PLA Matrix, as evidenced by the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) results.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study indicate that the introduction of surface modification using Benzoyl chloride in PLA/SCBF composites generally leads to an enhancement in both tensile strength and tensile modulus. However, a little reduction in the percentage elongation was observed. Furthermore, the chemical change resulted in an augmentation of the modulus of rupture, flexural modulus, impact strength, and hardness strength. Additionally, this study also demonstrated that the inclusion of fibres in the composites leads to a reduction in elongation, tensile strength, impact strength, and modulus of rupture. The increase in fibre loading is accompanied by a slight improvement in hardness strength. The chemical modification treatment of the SCBF fibre enhances the adhesive properties of the SCBF fibre, resulting in an improved interfacial bonding between the fabricated PLA-SCBF bio composites. The findings of the water uptake test demonstrated a reduction in the water absorption capacity of the modified composites. Additionally, a little decrease in weight loss was observed in the treated composites during an 80-day period of soil burial. The thermal study, namely the TGA and DTA curves, revealed a notable enhancement in the thermal characteristics of the composite material following the incorporation of benzoyl chloride. The fibre was found to include an inclusion of a Benzoyl group, as evidenced by FTIR analysis. Consequently, this resulted in enhanced adherence to the PLA matrix, as evidenced by scanning electron microscopy. The SCBF fibre exhibits

promising potential as a filler material in bio composites reinforced with natural fibres, hence presenting a viable alternative to the presently employed synthetic fibres.

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